

Ent-r-e-novators in action: final milestones, shared knowledge and lasting impact

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various actors
and break down
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A note from the Coordination Team

A journey coming to a close – but the impact remains

As the final weeks of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project approaches, this last edition of our newsletter brings together the key highlights from recent months, while also reflecting on the legacy of the work developed since 2022. Launched on 1 October 2022 and concluding on 30 September 2025, the Ent-r-e-novators project was funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme, through the call HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05. It aimed to strengthen research and innovation capacities across the E³UDRES² alliance by fostering open, engaged, and collaborative ecosystems.

The project was implemented by the six original members of the E³UDRES² alliance: IPS, STPUAS, MATE, UCLL, UPT, and ViA – institutions with diverse missions and contexts, working together to promote institutional transformation, stakeholder engagement, and inclusive R&I practices. Ent-r-e-novators also acknowledge the valuable dialogue with fellow projects from our Cluster projects ([AeroSTREAM](#), [Better Life](#), [BI4E](#), [EU4Climate](#), [EINSTEIN](#), [EULAC EnergyTran](#), [EXPER](#), [InCITIES](#), [Sustainable Horizons](#), and [Waterline](#)), which enriched our development process.

A very positive mid-term review reinforced our commitment and motivation to continue this shared journey with the same energy and ambition until the final stage.

In this closing edition, you'll find updates about some of our deliverables, thematic corner reflections, project voices, and public engagement activities – including the upcoming European Researchers' Night, which will coincide with the projects' final General Assembly. Ent-r-e-novators thanks all project teams and collaborators for their unwavering dedication and partnership over the past three years.

European Researchers' Night 2025: the Ent-r-e-novators project joins again

On 26 September 2025, the Ent-r-e-novators project will once again take part in the European Researchers' Night, one of the largest science communication events in Europe.

As in previous years, several Ent-r-e-novators' institutions will be actively involved in showcasing research to the wider public. Some events will take place on campus, while others will reach out directly to the local community. For example, the Polytechnic University of Setúbal will host activities in the city centre, engaging citizens of all ages with hands-on experiences and creative interactions.

This year, the event coincides with the final day of the 7th and final General Assembly of the Ent-r-e-novators project in Setúbal. It will mark a symbolic and meaningful moment to celebrate the link between research, innovation, and society.

The images below reflect the lively atmosphere and community engagement seen in past editions — from workshops and showcases to music and science-inspired dialogues.

Stay tuned as we share more details in the coming weeks. Let's celebrate research together, across cities, campuses and countries!

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Final General Assembly and Executive Board meetings mark the closing of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

As the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project nears its official conclusion, the 7th and final General Assembly (GnA) and the 12th and final Executive Board Meeting (ExB) will take place from 23 to 26 September 2025, in Setúbal, Portugal, hosted by the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS).

These events are embedded in the E³UDRES² Autumn Summit 2025, providing a final opportunity for strategic reflection, final reporting, and planning to sustain results beyond the project's lifetime.

Key meetings and sessions include:

- 25 September: Final General Assembly
A full-day session dedicated to reviewing the progress of all work packages, gathering feedback from the External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB), and preparing for the final project report and review. Discussions will also focus on the long-term implementation of project outcomes across partner institutions.
- 26 September: Final Executive Board Meeting (ExB-MTG12).
The closing Executive Board meeting will focus on financial reporting, deliverables and milestones, project risks and mitigation strategies, and the monitoring of post-project implementation plans.
- **Open Sessions for the Broader E³UDRES² Community.**
In addition to these internal meetings, the programme includes two international workshops, open to all members of the E³UDRES² community:

- **International Workshop on Open Science, Open Education and Open Innovation**
A session dedicated to sharing institutional strategies, challenges and progress in the adoption of open practices.
- **International Workshop on Citizen Science.** Exploring practical approaches to engaging citizens in research, with a focus on competencies, ethics and real-world applications.

These sessions provide a platform for exchanging knowledge and experiences across institutions, underscoring the project's commitment to engaged science and education.

Poster Session and ERN 2025

The event will also host a poster session featuring outputs from all project Work Packages, with each WP leader present to discuss the results. Posters will also be showcased at the European Researchers' Night 2025 (26 September), offering visibility to the broader public and reinforcing the project's engagement mission.

Sarah de Connick on the Thematic Corners | Citizen Science Corner KU Leuven

Sarah de Connick

Ent-r-e-novators recent video of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators series features insights from Sarah de Connick, highlighting the crucial role of Citizen Science in ensuring research outcomes make a tangible impact in the real world. This segment from the "Thematic Corners | Citizen Science Corner KU Leuven" highlights why engaging citizens and stakeholders from the outset is crucial for the effective implementation of research.

According to Sarah de Connick, a common challenge in traditional research is that results often fail to be implemented in the real world. This frequently occurs because the real-life context, including citizens and stakeholders, is not sufficiently considered from the very beginning of a research study. To truly make an impact, research needs to embrace the complexities of daily life and integrate the perspectives of those it aims to serve. However, achieving this requires a different set of skills than those typically found in traditional research. To address this need, a Delphi study was conducted with experts in citizen science. The study aimed to identify effective engagement strategies for involving citizens and stakeholders in research projects.

- The study's findings are significant, categorising eight distinct strategies for engagement. These strategies are also differentiated based on the skill level required for their application. Interestingly, some of these strategies, such as project design and planning, are also integral to traditional research. Still, they must be adjusted to fit the context of daily life and to engage citizens actively. For instance, when designing a project, researchers may need to differentiate between the intervention itself and its implementation, allowing for flexibility to adapt the research design to real-life conditions.
- By focusing on these human-centred approaches and developing new engagement skills, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, through initiatives like the Citizen Science Corner, is paving the way for research that is not only scientifically rigorous but also deeply relevant and impactful in addressing real-world challenges.
- To delve deeper into these crucial insights and explore the eight categories of engagement strategies, you can watch the full video with Sarah de Connick on the [E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators YouTube channel](#).

The EINSTEIN project's pathway towards sustainable bioelectronics

The EINSTEIN project is pioneering a new generation of biodegradable, non-toxic electronic devices using sustainable materials derived from plants and food residues. Funded under Horizon Europe's Widening participation and spreading excellence programme, the project brings together leading research institutions to spark scientific excellence and innovation capacity in Serbia and beyond.

Key achievements and scientific impact

At its core, EINSTEIN project represents a bold step toward sustainable electronics. Through interdisciplinary collaboration between the University of Novi Sad, five other partners from ecosystem, Vojvodina, Serbia and top European institutions – the Technical University of Denmark, Wageningen University from the Netherlands, and Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria – the project has produced breakthrough results in the development of organic field-effect transistors (OFETs) using natural, food-based, and food-waste-based materials. So far, five open-access papers have been published, with several appearing in high-impact journals. Notably, one of these papers was featured on the cover page of *Advanced Electronic Materials* in 2024, spotlighting EINSTEIN's contribution to cutting-edge sustainable electronics.

The project also contributed to institutional strengthening at UNS. During secondments to partner institutions, researchers were trained to use advanced scientific instruments. This expertise is now being transferred to colleagues at UNS, increasing local R&I capacity.

In parallel, EINSTEIN enhanced soft skills development through trainings on open science and gender equality, while expanding its scientific network through keynote lectures, international conferences, and the Winter School BioEL2025. Between 2024 and early 2025, the team submitted eight Horizon Europe proposals, with three approved for funding, including one European

Innovation Council (EIC) Pathfinder Open, one EIC Pathfinder Challenge, and one European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) Raw Materials project. These results demonstrate a growing ability to apply scientific outcomes directly and to raise the institution's overall competitiveness.

Environmental and technological innovation

EINSTEIN integrates environmental goals directly into its scientific research. The project valorised agricultural biowaste such as citrus peels, apple skins, and carrot residues into functional powders for electronics, directly supporting circular economy principles. By replacing toxic components with edible and biodegradable alternatives, EINSTEIN has laid the groundwork for green electronics that are safe, sustainable, and scalable. The project also launched the *EINSTEIN Agro Platform*, an open-access digital resource to promote sustainable agriculture and circular innovation. This platform provides an inventory of genetic resources for micronutrient-rich crops essential for healthy food production. Two additional platforms, EINSTEIN Food and EINSTEIN Bio, have also been initiated, further supporting interdisciplinary work in sustainable electronics, food, and biotechnology.

In parallel, EINSTEIN began working on nutricrop-based product concepts aimed at digestive health, opening future market potential in nutrifood and bio-based sensor applications.

Societal engagement and co-creation

From its inception, EINSTEIN has embraced responsible research and innovation. The project engaged citizens, policymakers, and SMEs through events like *One Health Serbia*, *Science Meets Public*, and *Researchers' Night*. The project also advanced gender equality and inclusiveness through a dedicated webinar and the *Women's Entrepreneurial Excellence* panel, fostering a more diverse research environment. Workshops on EU funding and project development encouraged early-career researchers to explore innovation pathways and entrepreneurship. During international events such as the Winter School BioEL2025, researchers established early-stage collaborations with renowned scientists, laying the foundation for future partnerships.

Building a greener future through innovation

EINSTEIN demonstrates how targeted support through Horizon Europe can accelerate scientific growth, innovation capacity, and international collaboration in Widening countries such as Serbia. Through scientific excellence, sustainable technology development, and active societal engagement, the project is contributing to Europe's green and digital transition, transforming waste into value and knowledge into long-term impact.

Spotlight on E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators: unpacking work package 6 Building a Human-Centred Research Ecosystem

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project continues to drive significant advancements in European higher education, and a key pillar of this transformation is Work Package 6 (WP6), which focuses on strengthening the research ecosystem by prioritising human resource development. The team behind WP6 recognised from the outset that the advancement of academic and research environments hinges directly on its people.

A Collaborative Path to Transformation

The core task of WP6 has been multifaceted: not only to analyse the existing landscape but also to forge a common strategy that enables the E³UDRES² alliance to grow collectively as partners, organisations, and a unified community. This journey began with honest self-reflection across all partner institutions. Each university conducted a deep situational analysis, identifying barriers and sharing diverse solutions related to research support, academic career development, mentoring, participation in decision-making, and the overall transparency and inclusiveness of human resource processes.

Vineta Silkāne, WP6 Coordinator

Building on this comprehensive assessment, WP6 developed a unified strategy meticulously. This strategy respects the unique specificities of each university while ensuring a cohesive direction for the entire alliance. The outcome is a joint action plan outlining concrete, measurable steps to bolster the research and innovation ecosystem within E³UDRES². Crucially, this plan was shaped through numerous discussions and workshops involving researchers, HR specialists, and top-level management, fostering a vital sense of understanding and trust that underpins future collaborative development.

Cultivating a Supportive Research Environment

The ambition of WP6 extends beyond mere definition; it is about cultivating a sustainable, resilient, and inclusive research environment. A strong human resources research ecosystem, as championed by WP6, begins with a clear vision of support for researchers. This support extends beyond formal HR procedures and professional development courses; it's fundamentally about fostering a culture where researchers feel heard and valued.

WP6 is actively laying the groundwork for such a culture by:

- Developing a participatory culture where researchers are engaged in decision-making processes as co-authors, not just recipients.
- Implementing mentoring programs that promote mutual learning among researchers at all career stages, from junior to highly qualified and leading academic staff.
- Promoting open career opportunities, recognizing and valuing mobility between universities as a benefit rather than a risk.
- Redefining academic leadership to encompass not just publications and funding acquisition, but also the vital ability to inspire, include, and support.

Navigating Challenges and Forging Solutions

Aligning strategies across diverse partner institutions presented inherent complexities, both formal and informal. These included varied national legislation, administrative practices, institutional structures, and informal factors like institutional culture, communication habits, and differing levels of development in research HR. Differences in institutional size and individual strategic goals also played a significant role. A particular challenge arose from the varying organizational structures of research, where research staff might be entirely separate from academic staff in some institutions, or functions might merge in others. Uneven progress in implementing institutional HR strategies for researchers – for instance, St. Pölten having already received the HR Excellence in Research quality mark while others are still working towards it – also created disparities in awareness and readiness for common standards.

Through a comprehensive SWOT analysis, WP6 identified common weaknesses limiting the research and innovation potential across E³UDRES² universities. To address these human resource and institutional challenges, the unified research HR development strategy proposes specific courses of action:

- Addressing the lack of career development systems: Implementing career counseling, individual development plans, and best practice exchange to support researchers' career growth effectively.
- Mitigating researcher overload: Emphasizing flexible work arrangements, including remote work options, and initiatives to promote work-life balance.
- Enhancing professional development: Introducing targeted training needs assessments, upskilling opportunities, and access to practically oriented training.
- Overcoming mobility and cooperation limitations: Expanding international opportunities beyond Erasmus+, with a greater focus on long-term researcher mobility and dedicated support mechanisms.

A Stronger, Future-Oriented Research Ecosystem

Ultimately, WP6 represents a pivotal shift from individual initiatives to a collective system. Within this system, researchers are empowered not merely as employees, but as active community members who can develop, collaborate, and contribute significantly to the university's advancement. This human-centred approach is the pathway to a stronger, more resilient, and future-oriented research ecosystem within the E³UDRES² alliance.

Stay tuned for more updates on how the Ent-r-e-novators project is transforming higher education and research into a more connected and innovative Europe!

To learn more about these fascinating insights, watch the full video with Vineta Silkāne and Katrīne Kūkoja on the [E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators YouTube channel](#).

24 August 2025

Luísa Carvalho IPS Vice-President

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Video Series: : Luísa Carvalho on the strategic value of Ent-r- e-novators

In a recent contribution to the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series, Luísa Carvalho, Vice President of the Polytechnic University of Setúbal for Research and Internationalisation, reflects on the long-term strategic relevance of the project for institutions like IPS and the broader E³UDRES² alliance.

Luísa Carvalho underlines that Ent-r-e-novators is more than a project — *“it’s a way to strengthen our research culture and create a sustainable network between E³UDRES² partners.”*

She further highlights the strategic importance of:

- Sharing research resources, infrastructures, and methodologies;
- Implementing common policies adapted to each institution’s context;
- Deepening cooperation across the alliance to amplify research excellence.

Concluding her reflection, Luísa Carvalho expresses strong confidence in the project’s future impact:

“The influence of Ent-r-e-novators in the years to come will be huge – thanks to this opportunity for collaboration and policy implementation.”

Watch the full video on the [Ent-r-e-novators YouTube channel](#).

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Video Series: Hannes Raffaseder on Transforming Higher Education

In the latest instalment of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series, we hear from Hannes Raffaseder, who shares profound insights into the evolving role of universities in a rapidly changing world and the crucial contributions of the E³UDRES² alliance.

Raffaseder highlights that universities must transform and develop in a future-oriented manner to address global challenges. A key aspect of this transformation is the interconnection of the four core missions of universities: education, research, innovation, and services, all developed with and for society. He emphasises the vital role of "ent-r-e-novators" – entrepreneurs, researchers, educators, and innovators – as the kind of people needed for this transformation across European higher education. St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences, a member of the E³UDRES² alliance, brings significant experience to the project.

Hannes Raffaseder, leader of the E³UDRES² alliance

The university is regionally anchored but possesses a global mindset, focusing on challenges related to knowledge exchange, innovation transformation, and startup support. They have a long-standing history of connecting education with applied research and have been awarded the Human Resources in Research award by the European Commission on multiple occasions over the years, actively supporting other E³UDRES² members in achieving this recognition.

- The Ent-r-e-novators project serves as a fundamental base for future collaboration and the support of innovation in higher education. It is instrumental in shaping the mindset and culture not only of St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences but also of the entire E³UDRES² European University Alliance. The project helps to achieve a more explicit focus on entrepreneurial innovation skills, linking these abilities to higher education and applied research. Furthermore, it bridges fundamental research with applied research, innovation, and research-based education, fostering new collaborations and innovative activities.
- Looking to the future, St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences views E³UDRES² as a "fully-fledged European university". They consider this European university a "joint spin-off" involving the E³UDRES² members, the European Commission, member states, and regions. The overarching vision is to create a "smart grid" of education, research, innovation, and services that spans across Europe and beyond, ultimately helping to ensure Europe remains a peaceful, prosperous, and globally competitive continent.
- The long-term impact of the Ent-r-e-novators project extends to contributing to new kinds of research and academic careers. Hannes Raffaseder points out that the lives of academics and researchers should evolve beyond just teaching and writing scientific publications. There is a crucial need for stronger connections to wider society and industries, and the Ent-r-e-novators project is designed to support these essential developments.

To learn more about these insights, watch the full video with Hannes Raffaseder on the [E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators YouTube channel](#).

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

Deliverable

5.2 Results

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Delivers Key Maturity Model for Citizen Science Engagement

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, dedicated to enhancing research excellence and impact, has released a crucial deliverable: the "Maturity model with engagement competences and engagement incompetences" (D5.2). This comprehensive report introduces a vital tool designed to guide researchers in effectively adapting and collaborating with citizens and stakeholders, ultimately ensuring research outcomes translate into real-world impact.

The Imperative for Citizen Engagement

The document highlights that the rising prevalence of citizen engagement in scientific research is transforming the field by democratizing the scientific process and directly addressing real-life challenges. Citizen Science (CS) is presented as a leading example, leveraging diverse voices, perspectives, and skills to advance scientific knowledge and foster deeper collaboration between science and society. Engaging the public brings valuable resources such as unique skills, computational power, and the capacity for massive data collection, while also enabling citizens to enhance their science literacy. It serves as a powerful instrument for mobilizing collective action against pressing global issues, like climate change.

However, this new collaborative approach necessitates a different set of skills than those commonly found in traditional research. To bridge this gap, the maturity model offers practical guidance for researchers aiming to strengthen their engagement competencies.

Introducing the Citizen Science Engagement Maturity Model

Developed as a dynamic "living document" within the Ent-r-e-novators project, the maturity model is rooted in the results of a Delphi Study carried out in Task 5.1. It departs from the established EURAXESS Researcher Profile Descriptors (R1-R4) and defines four distinct levels of expertise for citizen science engagement competencies:

- CS1: First Stage CS Competences
- CS2: Recognised Citizen Science Researcher
- CS3: Established Citizen Science Researcher
- CS4: Leading Citizen Science Researcher

The model identifies **eight key categories** of engagement competencies, detailing how expertise progresses within each:

- Project Design and Planning: From basic understanding to strategic leadership in international projects, emphasizing adaptive and inclusive designs.
- Communication: Advancing from basic interaction to developing comprehensive communication strategies for diverse groups, including digital storytelling.
- Understanding Context: Evolving from assessing barriers to providing solutions for complex engagement challenges.
- Networking and Outreach: Progressing from connecting citizens with researchers to building coalitions and creating innovative teams.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

Deliverable 5.2 Results

5. Transdisciplinary Teamwork: Developing from using advisory boards under supervision to leading and mentoring team performance in citizen science projects.
6. Training, Consultation, and Education: From participating in training to creating learning collaboratives and training for leadership roles.
7. Stakeholder and Citizen Incentives and Motivation: Advancing from proposing incentives under supervision to consulting on reward systems and establishing supportive environments.
8. Ethical Considerations: Progressing from knowledge of ethical considerations to supervising ethical aspects, integrating legal and ethical practices.

The model acknowledges that expertise levels can be fluid, meaning researchers may possess advanced skills in specific areas, regardless of their overall experience level.

Addressing Challenges and Fostering Self-Development

The primary challenge addressed by this deliverable is the need for researchers to develop competencies beyond traditional research methods to engage effectively with society. By outlining these specific engagement skills and their progression, the model implicitly helps researchers identify their "engagement incompetence" and provides a clear pathway for improvement.

To support self-development, the report highlights example resources for each of the eight competency areas, as well as general references on citizen science, quality standards, good practices, and funding. These materials aim to promote inclusive and collaborative approaches, as well as closer connections between researchers and the community.

This maturity model represents a significant step forward for the E³UDRES² Ent-re-novators project, equipping researchers with the necessary tools to drive impactful, societally relevant research and further solidify the alliance's role as a leader in entrepreneurial European higher education.

Follow the link to read the full deliverable [Deliverable 5.2 Maturity model with engagement competences and engagement incompetences](#)

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

Reflecting on Progress: highlights from Ent-r-e-novators' deliverables

As the Ent-r-e-novators project reaches the end of its second implementation period, it is timely to reflect on the publicly available deliverables produced and approved during the first reporting phase. These outputs provide a foundational basis for the project's strategic orientation, institutional development, and contribution to the European Research and Innovation landscape.

The early deliverables demonstrate the consortium's commitment to grounded, collaborative, and open approaches. Starting with the report on the research and innovation landscape across E³UDRES² institutions, the project mapped existing strengths, topic alignment with EU policies, and revealed strategic gaps, notably in areas such as medical sciences and low-carbon technologies. This effort was complemented by the development of a Joint Research and Innovation Agenda, which articulated shared priorities, built upon institutional analysis, and aligned with regional and global challenges.

Institutional maturity and readiness for open science, education, and innovation were another key focus. Deliverables in this area assessed organisational capacity, cultural dimensions, and existing practices, while also offering roadmaps and recommendations tailored to different levels of progress. This was done with careful attention to the diversity of institutional contexts within the alliance.

Complementing this, the work on engagement frameworks highlighted how to equip researchers and institutions with the competencies needed for citizen science. The engagement maturity model introduced a progression of skills and self-assessment tools to support the shift toward more inclusive research practices.

From a governance and sustainability perspective, several deliverables examined internal coordination, stakeholder involvement, and the project's external positioning. Strategies for policy engagement and science communication were outlined, showing how Ent-r-e-novators aims to amplify its voice and share its practices beyond the consortium.

Together, these documents reflect not only the progress made, but also a shared ambition to establish a sustainable ecosystem for open, engaged, and regionally relevant research and innovation. They are now all publicly accessible on the Ent-r-e-novators website, serving both as evidence of results achieved and as a resource for other institutions pursuing similar transformations.

As the project enters its final phase, these deliverables remain a key reference for what has been built so far – and for what comes next.

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